

Generalized Double Forward Derivatives

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Let $f(x)$ be a function and let $g(x)$ be its double forward derivative, then the future permutations of $f(x)$ can be mathematically expressed as:

$$f(x+h) = f(x) + hg(x) + \frac{h^2}{2!} \frac{d^2f}{dx^2} + \mathcal{O}(h^3)$$

We can derive the above expression by using Taylor's theorem. By Taylor's theorem, we have:

$$f(x+h) = f(x) + hf'(x) + \frac{h^2}{2!} f''(x) + \mathcal{O}(h^3)$$

Where $f'(x)$ is the first derivative and $f''(x)$ is the second derivative of $f(x)$. Substituting $f'(x)$ and $f''(x)$ with their respective forward derivatives $g(x)$ and $\frac{d^2f}{dx^2}$, we get the desired expression:

$$f(x+h) = f(x) + hg(x) + \frac{h^2}{2!} \frac{d^2f}{dx^2} + \mathcal{O}(h^3)$$

a)
$$\frac{d^2f}{dx^2} = \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+2h) - 2f(x+h) + f(x)}{h^2}$$

One example of a rotational group applied to the double forward derivative is the rotation group SO (3) . This group allows for a change of the basis vectors in 3 - dimensional space, which affects the derivatives of a function . For example, if we consider the double forward derivative of a function $f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ in the (x_1, x_2, x_3) coordinate system, then the derivative can be written as :

$$\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} = \sum_{k,l=1}^3 \frac{\partial x^k}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial x^l}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^k \partial x^l}$$

where $i, j, k, l = 1, 2, 3$. This equation shows how the double forward derivative of a function is affected by rotations in 3 - dimensional space . In terms of infinity tensor space, this equation implies that the derivatives of a function depend on the basis vectors of the space and how they are rotated . Map it onto the infinity tensor,

$$\mathbf{U}_{g_{a,b,c,d,e\dots f,g,h,i,j\dots}} = g^\wedge \Omega[f] \zeta[f] \times \kappa[f] \times \Omega[f] \int \exists [\theta, \mathbb{N} \partial_x \partial_\alpha \rho g^\wedge \Omega[\theta] d\theta ds d\delta d\eta],$$

where $g^\wedge \Omega[f]$ is the tensor's order, $\zeta[f]$ is the weight function,

$\kappa[f]$ is the factor of proportionality, and $\Omega[f]$ is the coefficient of

proportionality. and show a few options for rotation. The infinity tensor can be written as :

$$\mathcal{M}_{g_{abcd\dots fghij\dots}} = g^\Omega(f) \zeta(f) \kappa(f) \Omega(f) \int_{\mathcal{N}} d\theta ds d\delta d\eta \rho g^\Omega(\theta) \frac{\partial x}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta}$$

The rotation group SO (3) can be applied to the infinity tensor by defining the basis vectors of the space as the rotation axes, such that :

$$\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \mapsto \mathbf{x}' = R(\theta)\mathbf{x} = (x'_1, x'_2, x'_3)$$

where $R(\theta)$ is the rotation matrix . This means that the derivatives of the function $f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ in the new coordinate system can be written as :

$$\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x'_i \partial x'_j} = \sum_{k,l=1}^3 \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^k \partial x^l} \frac{\partial x^k}{\partial x'_i} \frac{\partial x^l}{\partial x'_j}$$

Thus, the double forward derivative of a function can be affected by rotations in 3 - dimensional space.